

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Compd	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ΔM $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	$Dq(E)$	$Dq(A)$	Dt	$-Ds$
	M	N						
Ni(BH) ₃	8.61 (8.90)	12.39 (12.65)	5	2.9	1 120	900	126	—
Ni(AB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	12.97 (13.02)	6.01 (6.21)	8	3.19	1 165	802	200	—
Ni(BB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	10.16 (10.21)	4.60 (4.87)	7	3.11	1 180	776	231	—
Co(BH)Cl ₂	13.18 (13.60)	9.43 (9.70)	15	4.86	1 131	718	236	1 366
Co(AB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	12.98 (13.06)	6.15 (6.37)	20	4.79	1 194	753	252	1 430
Co(BB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	9.96 (10.24)	5.01 (4.86)	18	5.10	1 220	771	257	1 652

complexes show high-spin octahedral configuration as the values lie in the range 4.97–5.10 B.M.¹⁶

In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, four bands have been observed at 9 900–10 100, 10 730–11 800, 17 800–18 600 and 28 300–29 400 cm⁻¹ regions. The first two bands are the split components of ν_1 and consequently can be assigned to the transitions ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ (ν_1) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (ν_1). The remaining two bands have been assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and are not greatly affected by the low symmetry environment on account of the fact that the levels concerned are ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ terms, which give rise to (${}^3A_{2g} + {}^3E_g$) in D_{4h} symmetry. In almost all the cases, only ν_1 has been found to split. Ligand field parameters $Dq(E)$ and Dt have been evaluated⁶ (Table 1). The distorted octahedral stereochemistry is further supported by the ratio ν_2/ν_1 which comes out to be 1.5–1.6, whereas the ratio in octahedral complexes¹⁷ should be about 1.8.

Octahedral cobalt(II) ion has the ground terms ${}^4T_{1g}$; three transitions are usually observed in its complexes ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1); ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). In lower symmetry D_{4h} , the ν_1 band is observed to split into two components¹⁸ (${}^4B_{2g}$, 4E_g) which depends upon the extent of magnitude of distortion produced by axial ligands. The ν_2 is also expected to split into ${}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4E_g(P)$. The ν_3 transition in octahedral stereochemistry transforms to ${}^4B_{1g}$ in D_{4h} symmetry and this transition is sometimes observed. The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes show bands in the region 6 370–7 270 (ν_1) and 8 580–9 250 cm⁻¹ (ν_2) accompanied by a shoulder in most of the cases in the region 15 040–17 240 cm⁻¹ and the third transition ν_3 has been found to split in all the complexes and their absorption bands appear in the 17 290–18 600 and 20 620–23 810 cm⁻¹ regions. These transitions have been assigned on the basis of D_{4h} symmetry. From these bands, radial parameters Ds and Dt have been evaluated. $Dq(E)$ has also been calculated (Table 1). The ratio ν_2/ν_1 being about 1.2, is a good evidence for pseudo-octahedral geometry¹⁹.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

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Stability Constants of Neodymium(III) Complexes with 8-Hydroxyquinoline and its Derivatives

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Manuscript received 6 August 1980, revised 15 June 1987,
accepted 6 July 1987

THE paper describes the complex formation of Nd^{III} with 8-hydroxyquinoline (OX), 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (OSA), 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (IOSA), 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline (NSOX), 5,7-dinitro-8-hydroxyquinoline

(DNOX), and 5-amino-8-hydroxyquinoline dihydrochloride (Am.Ox), by potentiometric technique. Complexation of many rare earth ions with ligands OX, OSA and IOSA in aqueous media have been reported¹. The present ligands have been chosen to see the effect of substituents on stability of the Nd^{III} complexes.

Experimental

A stock solution (0.02 M) of NdCl₃.xH₂O (IREDA, Bombay) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The metal content was estimated complexometrically with EDTA using bromopyrogallol red as indicator². Stock solution (0.005 M) of all the ligands were prepared in 80% (v/v) purified dioxan-water media. OX (B.D.H.), OSA (E. Merck), and IOSA (B.D.H.) were commercially available. NtOX, NsOX, DNOX and AmOX were synthesised by known methods³. The experimental findings on melting point and nitrogen estimations and ir frequencies of the ligands were in accord with literature values⁴. Solutions of carbon dioxide-free NaOH (Merck) and 0.4 M perchloric acid (Riedel) were prepared and standardised potentiometrically. Stock solution of sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was prepared in double-distilled water.

In the potentiometric titration procedure, 4.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand containing 0.02 M perchloric acid in the absence and in the presence of 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal was taken in 75% (v/v) dioxan-water media having a constant ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄). Hydrogen ion concentration in dioxan-water media was calculated by the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁵. The constants were evaluated by various computational methods⁶. Refined values of the constants are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND Nd^{III}-LIGAND CONSTANT IN 75% (v/v) DIOXAN-WATER MEDIUM

Temp. = 25°, Ionic strength (μ) = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand	Proton-Ligand constant		Nd ^{III} -Ligand constant		
	pK ₁ ^H	pK ₂ ^H	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃
OX	11.42	3.51	8.45	7.32	4.31
OSA	10.52	4.05	8.41	6.87	4.15
IOSA	8.96	2.50	7.34	5.12	4.32
NtOX	7.43	—	6.23	4.89	—
NsOX	7.22	—	4.02	3.52	—
DNOX	5.75	—	6.18	5.62	—
AmOX	10.20	—	8.27	6.64	—

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric study revealed the ligands OX, OSA and IOSA as biprotic and the ligands NtOX, NsOX, DNOX and AmOX as monoprotic. For complexation of Nd^{III} with OX, OSA, IOSA and AmOX, the values of $\bar{n}$ extended from 0 to 3, indicating the formation of three stepwise (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) complexes. Whereas in case of NtOX, NsOX and

DNOX, the $\bar{n}$ values extended from 0 to 2, indicating the formation of (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) complexes. Hydrolysis of [Nd^{III}-(OX)₃] complex was observed at pH 10.2, while those with NtOX, NsOX and DNOX were observed at pH 7.0. The trend in the stability of Nd^{III} complexes were in the ligand order, OX > OSA > AmOX > IOSA > NtOX > DNOX > NsOX, which is mostly in the order of decreasing ligand basicity (Table 1). In case of OX, OSA and IOSA, the substitution of SO₃H group and further addition of iodo group in parent OX analogue decrease the stability of complexes due to electron withdrawing properties of the added groups.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head of the Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur, for facilities.

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Formation Constants of Lanthanide Complexes with some Amino Acids

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Manuscript received 29 September 1986, revised 15 June 1987, accepted 6 July 1987

THE present paper describes a pH-metric study for the determination of formation constants of the La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} complexes with glycine, α-alanine, leucine or isoleucine.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Solutions for the equilibrium study were prepared in conductivity water. Free acid and metal contents of metal nitrate solutions were determined by acid-base² and complexometric³ methods.

Three sets of solutions containing (i) known amount of free HClO₄, (ii) solution (i) + known amount of ligand and (iii) solution (ii) + known